

Synthesis of 3-(or 5)-(Furyl or Thienyl)-5 (or 3)- (Hydroxy-Coumarinyl)-Isoxazoles

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The synthesis of eight new 3 (or 5)-(hydroxy coumarinyl)-5(or 3)-(furyl or thienyl)-isoxazoles have been reported, starting from the corresponding β -diketones. Their antifungal and seed-germination properties have been tested.

A number of isoxazole derivatives has been found to possess antibacterial¹, antitubercular² and antiviral activities. Cycloserine³, an isoxazole derivative is found to possess antitubercular⁴ and antibacterial⁵ activities. They are also found to be of considerable use in the treatment of Leprosy⁶. 3,5-Disubstituted isoxazoles⁷ with 2,4-dihydroxy-phenyl-substituent in 3-position of the isoxazole have been found to possess appreciable bacteriostatic and fungistatic activity. The activity of lactone structure is well known. It was, therefore, thought that isoxazoles with coumarinyl substituent (necessarily containing a phenolic group) and a heterocyclic substituent like furyl or thienyl should be active. With this view, this work was undertaken. The required β -diketones⁸ were prepared from *o*-hydroxy-acetyl-coumarins and furoyl or thenoyl chloride, using Baker-Venkataraman transformation. These were condensed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride to form 3,5-disubstituted isoxazoles.

A number of workers^{7,9} observed that this method yields a mixture of two-isomers (I and II). The isoxazoles formed were subjected to thin layer chromatography. In each case only one spot was observed showing the formation of only one product i.e., either I or II.

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The formation of 3,5-disubstituted isoxazoles was confirmed by I.R. spectral analysis. Bands at 895, 980, 1020, 1140, 1385, 1470, 1570 and 1615 cm^{-1} showed the presence of 3,5-disubstituted isoxazole ring^{7,10,11}, while the bands at 1630 and 1730 cm^{-1} showed the presence of a coumarinyl group. The presence of a phenolic group was shown by the bands at 1265 and 3130 cm^{-1} . The bands due to furyl group appeared at 865 and 3065 cm^{-1} , while the band due to thienyl appeared at 700 to 730 cm^{-1} . A representative method for the synthesis of the isoxazoles is given below.

Synthesis of 3-(or 5)-(furyl or thienyl)-5(or 3)-(hydroxy-coumarinyl)-isoxazoles : A mixture of 1-(2-furyl or 2-thienyl)-3-(hydroxy-coumarinyl)-propane-1 : 3-dione (1 gm), methanol (40 ml) and hydroxyl-amine hydrochloride (2 gms) was boiled for about 4 to 6 hr. The solid obtained after cooling was washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid, methanol or ethanol.

Table I shows the melting points etc. of the synthesised isoxazoles.

TABLE I

3(or 5)2'-furyl or 2'-thienyl)-5(or 3)-(hydroxy-coumarinyl)-isoxazoles.

Compound	M.P. °C	Calculated		Found	
		C%	H%	C%	H%
1. 3-(or 5)-(2'-furyl)-5(or 3)-[8''-(4''-methyl-7''-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-isoxazole	159	66.01	3.559	65.75	3.777
2. 3(or 5)-(2'-Furyl)-5(or 3)-[8''-(4''-methyl-6''-ethyl-7''-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-isoxazole	227	67.66	4.451	67.39	4.808
3. 3(or 5)-(2'-Furyl)-5(or 3)-[6''-(4''-methyl-7''-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-isoxazole	251	66.01	3.559	65.55	3.974
4. 3(or 5)-(2'-Furyl)-5(or 3)-[6''-(4''-methyl-5''-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-isoxazole	165	66.01	3.559	65.77	3.854
5. 3(or 5)-[(2'-Thienyl)-5(or 3)-[8''-(4''-methyl-7''-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-isoxazole	176	62.76	3.385	62.48	3.714
6. 3(or 5)-(2'-Thienyl)-5(or 3)-[8''-(4''-methyl-6''-ethyl-7''-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-isoxazole	190	64.59	4.249	64.34	4.616
7. 3(or 5)-(2'-Thienyl)-5(or 3)-[6''-(4''-methyl-7''-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-isoxazole	264	62.76	3.385	62.41	3.501
8. 3(or 5)-(2'-Thienyl)-5(or 3)-[6''-(4''-methyl-5''-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-isoxazole	206	62.76	3.385	62.26	3.608

Physiological activity of various isoxazoles :

(a) *Fungistatic activity* : 0.001M solution of compound No. 1 to 8 showed 44, 11, 0, 100, 5, 55, 16 and 11 percent inhibition respectively of the growth of *Alternaria solani*.

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(b) *Seed germination activity* : The seed germination activity was tested with *Mustard Seeds*. Compounds No. 1 to 8 showed 100, 90, 50, 0, 0, 80 and 0 percent germination respectively. The percentage germination in the case of compound No. 1, 2, 4 and 7 was 100, 90, 50, and 80 but the number of leaves formed were 4, 4, 4 and 2, respectively. This showed that though compound No. 4 inhibits the germination to 50%, the germinated seeds grow vigorously than the rest.

(c) *Antitrichinella spiralis activity* : These compounds were tested for *Antitrichinella spiralis* activity in mice. A dose of 50 mg/kg was given to a mouse and observed for a day. 3 (or 5)-(2'-Furyl)-5 (or 3)-[6''-(4''-methyl-5''-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-isoxazole, showed 21.4% decrease in the growth of antitrichinella worms.

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